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- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
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THE PROBLEMS OF REMOTE LEARNING TECHNOLOGY AND GLOBAL TRENDS IN UNIVERSITY EDUCATION DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: This article focuses on the principal developments in higher education, particularly massification and globalization. These changes are accompanied by transformative shifts in educational technologies, especially in the field of information and communication technologies (ICT). The main stages in the evolution of distance education are analyzed, and the role of ICT in this process is demonstrated. The paper addresses the issue of electronic educational content in distance learning, including within the framework of web-based education. Foreign and domestic experience in structuring content for Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) is analyzed, and their potential and existing challenges are assessed. The authors also describe their own experience in developing and implementing multimedia modules close in format to MOOCs and present their pedagogical structure.

Key words: educational trends, massification and globalization of higher education, distance learning technologies, Massive Open Online Courses, e-learning, web-based education, multimedia modules.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqola oliy ta'lim tizimidagi asosiy rivojlanish tendensiyalariga, xususan uning ommaviylashuvi va globallashuviga bag'ishlangan. Ushbu o'zgarishlar ta'lim texnologiyalaridagi, ayniqsa axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari (AKT) bilan bog'liq tub yangilanishlar bilan chambarchas bog'liqdir. Masofaviy ta'limning rivojlanish bosqichlari tahlil qilinib, AKTning ushbu jarayondagi roli yoritib berilgan. Masofaviy ta'limda elektron ta'lim kontenti muammolari, jumladan veb-ta'lim doirasida ko'rib chiqiladi. Ommaviy ochiq onlayn kurslar (MOOC) doirasida ta'lim kontentini shakllantirish bo'yicha xorijiy va mahalliy tajribalar tahlil qilinadi. Ularning salohiyati va mavjud muammolari baholanadi. Shuningdek, mualliflar MOOC formatiga yaqin bo'lgan multimedia modullarini ishlab chiqish va joriy etish bo'yicha o'z tajribalarini bayon etib, ularning pedagogik tuzilmasini tavsiflaydilar.

Kalit so'zlar: ta'lim tendensiyalari, oliy ta'limning ommaviylashuvi va globallashuvi, masofaviy ta'lim texnologiyalari, ommaviy ochiq onlayn kurslar, elektron ta'lim, veb-ta'lim, multimedia modullari.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются ключевые тенденции развития высшего образования, прежде всего связанные с его массовизацией и глобализацией. Указанные изменения сопровождаются революционными сдвигами в образовательных технологиях, в частности в сфере информационно-коммуникационных технологий (ИКТ). Проанализированы основные этапы эволюции дистанционного образования и показана роль ИКТ в его развитии. Рассматривается проблема электронного образовательного контента в дистанционном обучении, в том числе в рамках веб-образования. Проанализирован зарубежный и отечественный опыт структурирования контента в массовых открытых онлайн-курсах (МООС). Оценены их потенциал и существующие проблемы. Авторы также описывают собственный опыт разработки и внедрения мультимедийных модулей, близких по формату к МООС, и представляют их педагогическую структуру.

Ключевые слова: образовательные тренды, массовизация и глобализация высшего образования, технологии дистанционного обучения, массовые открытые онлайн-курсы, электронное обучение, веб-образование, мультимедийные модули.

INTRODUCTION

Notwithstanding the prevailing issues and critiques regarding the current state of higher education, a study conducted by the Public Opinion Foundation on June 15, 2014, reveals that 57% of Russians believe that obtaining higher education facilitates success in life [5]. This perception substantiates a significant trend in contemporary culture—the massification of higher education. Higher education is gradually transforming from an elite system into a mass phenomenon. This transformation does not imply the disappearance of leading

universities; rather, it reflects a substantial increase in both the number of higher education institutions and the student population. In the United States, 40% of individuals aged 18–24 was enrolled in universities in 2012, compared with 24% in 1973.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In 2012, up to 39% of young people in the countries of the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) graduated from higher education institutions, while up to 50% of adults possessed higher education degrees. Australia, Denmark, Poland, and Iceland demonstrate particularly high participation rates, exceeding 50%, whereas Mexico, Saudi Arabia, and Turkey exhibit the lowest rates, at approximately 25%. In this comparative context, China's achievements appear relatively modest, accounting for only 14% [2].

In Russia, from the 1970s–1980s, the proportion of students ranged from 3% to 7% of the total population, and only about 70 new higher education institutions were established during the postwar period. At present, the number of higher education institutions has doubled (excluding other fields), and student enrollment has increased by 2.3 times. A. Fursenko, former Minister of Education and Science of the Russian Federation (2004–2012), proposed the introduction of an admission “cut-off threshold” based on Unified State Examination (USE) scores, setting a minimum score for university admission and a higher score for eligibility for state-funded education (for example, 40% and 60% on a 100-point scale). Although seemingly rational, such measures may provoke social tension among young people under current conditions, given the significant social role played by higher education institutions.

According to Rosstat statistics, in 2013 Russia had 1,046 higher education institutions (609 public and 437 private), with a total enrollment of 6,073.9 thousand students (5,143.8 thousand in public institutions). Despite projections by the Ministry of Economic Development indicating a decline of more than one million students by 2015 due to demographic trends and institutional optimization [25], Russia ranked third globally (after the USA and Finland) in the number of students per 10,000 population–510 [20]. In the Republic of Tatarstan, this figure amounted to 387 in 2013.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The student-to-faculty ratio increased from 9.4 to 12. In 2012, the higher education system required 671,702 academic staff members; by 2018, this number had declined to 472,750, resulting in a 28% increase in the teaching workload. Regional university centers also experienced growth in student enrollment. In the Republic of Tatarstan, student numbers reached their peak in the 2009-2010 academic year at 220,191, after which enrollment declined to 190,490. A substantial proportion of students are enrolled in part-time (correspondence) programs, where maintaining educational quality and academic standards presents significant challenges. Government representatives, industry stakeholders, and the general public are increasingly expressing concern about the quality of higher education. According to Ya. Kuzminov, V. Mau, and S. Sinelnikov-Murylev, the existing admission system does not adequately filter out institutions with limited development potential, while formal performance indicators are easily manipulated, resulting in minimal entry barriers within the higher education sector [13].

Another significant trend is the growing globalization of higher education and the intensification of academic mobility. According to the OECD report *Education at a Glance 2012*, the number of students studying abroad more than quadrupled, increasing from 2.1 million in 2000 to 4.1 million in 2010.

Equally important are transformative advances in instructional technologies driven by the Internet and modern multimedia tools. The interaction of these technological developments with economic constraints and innovation-oriented development objectives has significantly shaped discussions on the modernization of higher education. A sociological study conducted by the authors indicates that educational innovation is most frequently associated with the use of information and communication technologies (41% of respondents) and distance learning formats (20%) [6, 22]. Distance education has undergone several stages of development, evolving from correspondence-based instruction delivered through postal communication to contemporary web-based learning platforms. Today, web-based education and MOOCs represent a new, fully remote form of education. Platforms such as Coursera, edX, and Udacity offer numerous courses to millions of learners worldwide. Despite optimistic expectations, MOOCs should be regarded as a valuable complement rather than a replacement for traditional university education, particularly in the context of continuing and professional education.

The authors also describe their experience in developing and evaluating multimedia modules designed as autonomous learning units for the formation and assessment of professional competencies. These modules incorporate video cases, methodological guidelines, student workbooks, and role-playing scenarios. Each

module contains academic content, professional situations, examples of common mistakes, and interactive decision-making tasks. The implementation of such modules contributes to enhanced skills development, supports quality assurance in education, protects institutional intellectual property, and aligns with the learning preferences characteristic of Generation Z.

CONCLUSION

The advancement of remote learning technologies through integrated virtual training systems enables higher education institutions to effectively address the challenges of massification and globalization while preserving educational quality. Although online education is expected to continue its expansion, traditional universities will retain their essential role, particularly in socialization, research, and cultural transmission. At the same time, the growing prominence of global university brands poses risks of cultural homogenization, which necessitates deliberate and sustained attention from national authorities and institutional leadership.

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 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Mas'ul muharrir: Ramzidin Ashurov

Ingliz tili muharriri: Murod Xoliyorov

Musahhah: Alibek Zokirov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2026. №1

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"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.